

Modeling subcutaneous strains from fingertip surface deformations

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Abstract. Understanding how external contact forces translate into internal mechanical states of the fingertip remains a central challenge for tactile biomechanics and neuroscience. Here, we present a novel experimental–computational framework that links high-resolution measurements of fingertip surface deformations to subject-specific finite element (FE) models derived from magnetic resonance imaging. Fingertips are loaded against a transparent glass plate while stereo imaging reconstructs three-dimensional skin deformations, which are used to constrain FE simulations and evaluate their ability to reproduce observed deformation patterns. This inverse modeling approach provides a non-invasive window onto subcutaneous mechanical states. Ongoing data acquisition aims to probe anatomically informed and ecologically relevant fingertip mechanics across participants.

Keywords: Bio-mechanics, Finite Element Modeling, Inverse Modeling

1 Introduction

Recent experimental advances enable high-resolution measurements of fingertip surface during contact, revealing rich spatiotemporal strain patterns associated with phenomena such as partial slip and contact transitions [1, 2, 3]. These measurements prove highly informative for interpreting tactile afferent responses and grip control mechanisms [4, 5]. However, superficial observations alone lack the depth component that may be crucial to understanding mechanosensory transduction mechanisms [6]. Finite element (FE) models offer a powerful framework to bridge this gap, but their results critically depend on realistic anatomy and material properties [7].

This work introduces a new experimental–computational approach to infer the mechanical properties of fingertip tissues by directly linking measured surface deformations to subject-specific FE simulations. Fingertips are loaded against a transparent glass plate while a stereo camera system reconstructs 3D surface deformations of the glabrous skin. In parallel, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is used to capture individual fingertip anatomy and generate realistic meshes for numerical modeling. By reproducing the experimental loading conditions in FE simulations and comparing predicted and measured surface deformations, we aim to identify material parameters that

minimize the discrepancy between simulations and experiments, hopefully indicating their biological consistency.

2 Methods

2.1 MRI acquisition and Model geometry

Using a 3T scanner, T1-weighted images of the hand are acquired in the coronal plane with an isotropic in-plane resolution of 0.27 mm and a slice thickness of 0.30 mm (Fig 1.A). The Field of View is placed to prioritize the quality of the images of the index and middle fingertips. The hand is stabilized using 3D-printed support and foam. The setup prevents movements and allows imaging of the fingertips without any contact on the palmar side of the fingers.

A custom Python pipeline was implemented to segment the MRI volumes into three different layers corresponding to skin, subcutaneous soft-tissues, and bone. Then, a marching cube algorithm [8] is used to convert the voxels of each layer into a mesh. The mesh is then processed using Gmsh [9] to improve its quality (Fig 1.B).

2.2 Mechanical stimuli and FE simulation

The experimental setup used to apply mechanical stimuli and record stereo images of the fingertips has already been described in Doumont et al. 2025, 2026 [1, 2]. Briefly, a robotic platform applies controlled forces (Fig 1.D, E.) to the fingertip through a transparent glass plate. At the same time, a stereo camera array captures full-field fingertip surface deformations for 3D reconstruction based on Digital Image Correlation (xDIC) (Fig 1.C). Tangential and normal forces are monitored during the trials.

The 3D-reconstructed surface is used to constrain FE simulations on the MRI-based mesh and to compute an accuracy score for each simulation, representing how well the simulation succeeds in reproducing external deformation patterns. To this end, the FE mesh is registered to the reconstructed surface. Skin surface points that contact the glass plate during the stimulation are used to impose displacement boundary conditions on the model, while all remaining surface points serve as a reference to evaluate the agreement between simulated and experimental surface deformations (Fig 1.B, C).

3 Future perspective and Conclusion

This work introduces a methodological framework based on the central premise that fingertip surface deformations reflect the mechanical constraints in underlying tissues. We proposed an inverse modeling approach that could provide a non-invasive window onto internal stresses and strains, hardly accessible otherwise (Fig. E). This work opens new perspectives for understanding fingertip mechanics during natural interactions. Experimental acquisition is ongoing. The objective is to collect paired MRI and fingertip loading data from around 25 participants, with an experimental protocol designed to probe complex and ecologically relevant loading conditions.

Fig. 1 Overview of the experimental and modeling framework. A) MRI image of the hand and a zoom on the sagittal view of the index fingertip. B) Model of the finger showing the projection of the segmented mesh (model, above) on the 3D reconstruction from the stereo cameras (in green, below). C) Experimental view from one camera and the tracked points in 3-D in green. D) Forces measured during the loading of the fingertip on the plate. E) Strain field inside the volume of the finger evaluated by the model simulation at given sampled forces.

Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange. This project requires strong interdisciplinary collaboration. Advances in solid mechanics and inverse problem theory are needed to formalize parameter identification and uncertainty. Input from histology and anatomy can guide which tissue compartments and geometric features are essential to capture fingertip mechanical behavior. Finally, collaboration with neuroscience may help relate inferred internal deformations to tactile afferent responses.

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Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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